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Ultra-high-frequency Love surface acoustic wave device for real-time sensing applications

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ABSTRACT Love surface acoustic wave (L-SAW) devices are ideal for real-time sensing applications. High miniaturization and sensitivity are desirable in particular for point of care diagnostics or on-site measurements. It is possible to enhance both these parameters by increasing the working frequency of these devices, but this is still a challenge. Indeed, the ultra-high frequency (UHF) range has not been explored yet for L-SAW sensing devices because it requires non-trivial fabrication and measurement setup. Here, we present a multiplexable, highly miniaturized UHF L-SAW device for real-time sensing applications. The sensor performance was first tested with mixtures of different volume percentages of isopropyl alcohol (IPA) in water. Measurements of phase and amplitude (related to change of density and viscosity, respectively) show higher sensitivity and dynamic range than a representative 100 MHz L-SAW sensor. Then, we measured the adsorption kinetics of three different concentrations of bovine serum albumin (BSA) in water on the sensor surface, demonstrating biomolecule detection. The all-electrical readout system as long as the small dimensions make the presented device particularly promising for portable UHF sensing platforms. Nonetheless, the higher sensitivity and dynamic range obtained with respect to a representative 100 MHz L-SAW sensor as long as the real-time measurements of the BSA adsorption (with an estimated limit of detection of 90 ng/mm²) show that UHF Love SAW sensors have the potential to be used for bio-sensing applications, such as point of care diagnostics.

INDEX TERMS Biosensors, surface acoustic waves, ultra-high frequency, microfluidics.

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the last decades, the surface acoustic wave (SAW) technology has attracted the attention of the scientific community developing lab-on-chips (LOCs) [1]–[4]. LOCs are devices not bigger than few square centimeters that integrate one or more laboratory functions in a single chip. In this context, SAW-based devices have been extensively explored for controlling and actuating particles and fluids in the microfluidic regime [5]–[10]. They are also useful tools for cell manipulation [11]–[14] and for the enhancement of microfluidic sensor functionalization [15], [16]. These systems have the advantage of being fast, cheap, portable, wirelessly addressable and easy to operate. Moreover, they have the potential to be combined with the CMOS technology for developing integrated platforms [17], [18]. SAW devices have also gained particular interest for bio-sensing applications, such as environmental analysis [19]–[21], food safety control [22], [23] and point-of-care

diagnostics [24]–[26]. SAWs can be divided in two main types, depending on their polarization: Rayleigh (R) and Love (L) SAWs, vertically and horizontally polarized with respect to the crystal surface, respectively. Typical working frequencies of SAW sensors are in the range of 10–300 MHz. However, it is expected that the sensor sensitivity can increase with the working frequency [27]. For example, our group recently introduced an ultra-high-frequency (UHF) R-SAW resonator biosensor that reached a limit of detection (LoD) far better than that of standard commercial quartz crystal microbalances (QCMs) [28]. Nonetheless, R-SAWs can only operate in dry conditions, which hinders their use for real-time detection in liquids. L-SAWs, thanks to their shear-horizontal polarization, do not couple with liquids and are thus compatible with measurements in wet conditions. Another advantage of L-SAW biosensors is the presence of the waveguide layer, that has also a protective role for the interdigital transducers (IDTs) from possible external

deterioration sources. If soluble polymers are chosen as waveguide layers, multiple uses of each device can be easily made by cleaning them off with their solvents [29]. More in general, it has been suggested that L-SAW devices are one of the best technologies for bio-sensing [30], [31]. They have been exploited for the detection of proteins and nucleic acids [32]–[37], cell growth [38]–[41] and organic molecules [42], [43]. To date, the UHF range (from 300 MHz to 3 GHz) has not been explored yet for L-SAW sensors.

Here, we demonstrate the first UHF L-SAW device for real-time sensing applications. The technology here exploited is suitable for the integration with standard CMOS devices and wirelessly addressable.

II. THE DEVICE

A. DEVICE DESIGN AND REALIZATION

The chip consists of a 2 cm × 2 cm substrate of 36° YX LiTaO₃ (LT) on which four delay lines (DLs) were fabricated (Figure 1a) in order to enable multiplexed measurements. Following the analytical design rules, reported for example in [44], we aimed at maximizing the Love wave generation and transmission in order to ensure a proper electro-mechanical configuration for the biosensing experiments. Each DL (the red box in Figure 1a, and schematized in details in Figure 1b) consists in two split-finger IDTs (12.5 finger pairs, metallization ratio = 50%) and two conventional $\lambda/4$ reflectors (24 fingers), where λ is the SAW wavelength. Both IDTs and reflectors were fabricated by depositing a Ti/Au (15 nm/140 nm) bilayer on the LT substrate and have 4.16 μm periodicity (p), corresponding to λ . The nominal resonance frequency f_0 is 1 GHz. Split-fingers width is 520 nm, whereas the reflectors electrodes width is 1.04 μm . IDTs and reflectors acoustic apertures are 800 μm (A1) and 900 μm (A2), respectively. The reflector distance (L1) is 2.08 mm and the delay line length (L2) is 2 mm (see the schematics in Figure 1b). Split-finger IDTs and the reflector design were chosen to avoid reflections and to improve the frequency response of the L-SAW device [30]. For the chip fabrication detailed protocol refer to the Supplementary Material. IDT impedance matching (50 Ω) was achieved by tuning the split-finger IDT aperture and the number of finger pairs [45] and verified by device testing. The DLs were connected via coplanar waveguides and wire bonded to a printed circuit board (PCB). In order to produce Love waves, a waveguide layer must be added to the LT chip whose 36° YX cut supports surface skimming bulk waves [46]. Polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) was selected as the waveguide material. The use of polymers is interesting from the point of view of the sensitivity, since they have low shear velocity (1200 m/s in the case of PMMA). Another advantage of using PMMA is their easy and clean removal. In this case the waveguide layer thickness optimization can be much more straightforward than for waveguides that can't be removed without damaging the chip [30]. The PMMA waveguide layers were deposited on the device by spin-coating solutions of PMMA (950 000 g/mol) in anisole. The polymer layers were then cured at room temperature

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overnight. Depending on the spin speed and PMMA concentration, waveguide thicknesses in the range of 50–550 nm were obtained, as determined by profilometry measurements. A polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) well was placed by conformal bonding on each DLs to confine the fluid on the sensing area [47]. The well was made by manually punching a 5-mm-diameter hole into the PDMS. After filling the well with the solution (25 μL), it was covered with a glass coverslip to prevent unwanted evaporation during the experiments.

B. CHARACTERIZATION AND OPTIMIZATION

For the electrical measurements, we used a vector network analyzer (VNA, ENA Series Network Analyzer, E5071C, Agilent). Each measurement was acquired by averaging 5 spectra with an intermediate frequency bandwidth of 70 kHz. First, we tested the L-SAW device by measuring the reflected power spectrum of the two IDTs of each DL. Figure 2a and Figure 2b show the reflected power spectra S11 and S22, respectively, of a representative DL before (green line in Fig. 2a and b) and after (blue line in Fig. 2a and b) waveguide thickness optimization. Figure 2c shows the transmitted power spectra before and after waveguide thickness optimization of a representative DL where the SAW resonance is identified at $f = 0.955$ GHz. The resonance frequency was calculated by prior smoothing the transmitted power spectrum and then extrapolating its maximum (see Supplementary material for further details). Figure 2d shows the normalized transmitted power variation of the L-SAW devices in correspondence of the resonance frequency of the DL as a function of the PMMA layer thickness. The normalized transmitted amplitude at the resonance frequency vs. waveguide thickness has a peak in correspondence of the optimal SAW transmission (S21) along the DL where maximal sensitivity is consequently expected [48]–[50]. It can be seen that the curve in Figure 2d has a maximum at the waveguide thickness of ~ 125 nm, indicating this value as the optimal thickness for maximizing the sensor mass sensitivity. More specifically, this waveguide ensures that more than the 99% of the injected power is transmitted through the DL.

III. SENSING EXPERIMENTS

A. DENSITY/VISCOSITY SENSING

The UHF L-SAW sensor performance was first tested with mixtures of different volume percentages of isopropyl alcohol (IPA) in water. As the volume of IPA increases, the density of the solutions decreases whereas the viscosity increases. The phase and the amplitude of L-SAW devices are highly sensitive to mass and viscosity changes [51]. We obtained phase and amplitude response curves by measuring the transmitted spectra at different IPA concentrations in water (Figure 3a). Figure 3b shows the transmitted phase (black circles) and amplitude (blue squares) at the resonant frequency of the sensor for increasing IPA concentration in water. Error

bars were calculated as the standard deviation of the sensor signal over the experiment time. Comparing the phase and amplitude trends with the ones reported for a representative 100 MHz L-SAW sensor, we observe that our UHF L-SAW sensor has a higher dynamic range and a higher sensitivity to density changes. In particular, it resulted in a 2.5-fold improvement of the sensitivity with respect to ref. [52] (see Supplementary Material for more details), suggesting that UHF devices can perform better than standard low frequency sensors.

B. BIO-SENSING

We tested the UHF L-SAW sensor with a biological analyte: bovine serum albumin (BSA). We tested three different concentrations of BSA in water: 0.1 mg/ml, 1 mg/mL and 10 mg/ml. BSA was chosen since serum albumin is the most plentiful protein in blood plasma; in particular, it plays a very important role in maintaining the oncotic pressure of blood and its concentration is considered a reliable sign of health (*i.e.*, it is a critical indicator for kidney damage) [53]. We injected 25 μ L of the BSA solution into the PDMS well on top of a sensor area at time $t = 0$ and we monitored the signal for 800 s to follow the protein adsorption kinetics up to its saturation on the sensor surface. We followed this procedure for each concentration. Considering that the well diameter is 5 mm, that we injected 25 μ l of protein solution and that it is known from literature that about 70% of BSA is adsorbed onto PMMA [12], we can estimate that the surface protein density that we measured in the case of the smallest BSA concentration (0.1 mg/ml) was 90 ng/mm². A custom-made LabView® software was developed to collect and process the transmitted phase spectra from the VNA. The signal was acquired every 20 s. Table 1 reports the fundamental parameters for the acquisition and data processing that were used for the bio-sensing experiments, and figure 4 reports the experimental setup and software algorithms.

TABLE I
PARAMETERS FOR ACQUISITION AND DATA PROCESSING

Parameter	Description	Value
Δt	time interval between software acquisitions	8 s
T	software acquisition time	12 s
N	number of points in frequency per spectrum	1601
IF-BW	intermediate frequency bandwidth	70 kHz
f_0	center frequency	0.955 GHz
f_{SPAN}	frequency span	200 MHz
s	smoothing	1.5%
P	RF power	0 dBm

A schematic of the modification of the sensor surface and its phase response over time is depicted in Figure 5a and Figure 5b. Figure 5c shows the transmitted phase signal at the resonance frequency during BSA adsorption on the sensor surface at the three concentrations tested. Black, red and blue dots represent the phase shift over time due to 0.1 mg/ml, 1

mg/ml and 10 mg/ml BSA concentration, respectively. In order to compare our results with existing literature, data were fitted with an exponential curve. This analytical description allows us to estimate the characteristic time (τ) of the observed phenomena (Adj. R-square ≥ 0.98). As shown in the inset of Figure 5c, the characteristic times (140 s, 23 s and 10 s for 0.1 mg/ml, 1 mg/ml and 10 mg/ml, respectively) followed the expected trend $\tau \propto \frac{1}{c_0}$, where c_0 is the injected BSA concentration. The analytical description of the BSA adsorption is therefore consistent with what found in literature [54], [55]. All experiments started after a step of sensor conditioning in water that was necessary for signal stabilization. By estimating the LoD as 3σ (where σ is the standard deviation of the blank) [56] we obtained a LoD of 50 μ g/ml.

The estimated LoD of 50 μ g/ml along with its all-electrical readout system demonstrate that this device has all the potential to be used for bio-sensing applications, such as point of care diagnostics and on-site measurements. In particular, this sensor is compatible with the range of variation of serum albumin as biomarker for risk prediction in various clinical conditions.

IV. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we realized a highly miniaturized UHF L-SAW sensor. The sensor is designed to be compatible with multiplexed measurements and to be easily integrated into microfluidic systems. The all-electrical readout system and wireless addressability typical of SAW devices -as shown for example in [57], [58]-, along with its sensing performance make this UHF L-SAW device highly suitable for many sensing applications. For example, on-site and point of care (PoC) analyses are feasible with the presented device, opening promising perspectives for highly sensitive and portable UHF Love-SAW platforms.

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FIGURE 1. Chip illustration and electrical connections. (a) Schematics of the UHF L-SAW device. (a) Photograph of a representative device connected to a PCB for electrical readout (scale bar is 3 mm). The first inset is a zoomed image of one of the 4 sensors consisting in a delay line composed by two IDTs and two reflectors (scale bar is 1 mm). The second inset is a representative scanning electron microscopy detail of an IDT and a reflector (scale bar is 10 μm). (b) Sensor schematics. L1 and L2 represent the IDT-IDT distance and the reflectors distance, respectively. A1 and A2 represents the apertures of the IDTs and reflectors, respectively. IDTs electrodes have a width of $\lambda/8$ (split-finger configuration) and reflectors electrodes have a width of $\lambda/4$. A cross section of the sensor is shown in the bottom right panel (not to scale).

FIGURE 2. Device electrical characterization and waveguide thickness optimization. (a-b) Representative reflected power spectra of the IDTs composing the DL. (c) Representative transmitted power spectra of a DL. Green and blue lines represent, respectively, the signal with and without the optimized waveguide layer. Resonant frequency $f_0 = 0.955$ GHz. (d) Normalized transmitted power signal at f_0 at increasing PMMA waveguide thicknesses. Optimal power transmittance was achieved for a thickness of ~ 125 nm.

FIGURE 3. Sensor performance characterization. (a) Representative transmitted phase and power spectra at increasing concentrations of IPA in water. (c) Transmitted phase (black squares) and power (blue circles) signals at f_0 for increasing concentrations of IPA in water.

FIGURE 4. Experimental setup and algorithms. **A)** Scheme of the experimental setup: the device under test (DUT) is measured by a VNA acquiring two RF reflected power spectra (S11 and S22) and one transmitted spectrum (S21) per sensor. The VNA communicates with a LabView® custom-made software for spectra acquisition and data analysis (*i.e.*, smoothing and resonance signal finding). **B)** LabView custom software workflow. The acquisition starts with the user input of the initial parameters. Next, the software loops with Δt interval, repeating spectra collection and saving. Resonance signal finding is applied to the smoothed spectra to generate the sensorgrams.

FIGURE 5. Real-time detection of BSA adsorption. (a) Schematics of the BSA adsorption timeline. Time $t = 0$ s refers to the injection of the solution on the sensor. $t = 800$ s refers to the BSA saturation condition on the sensor area. Representative transmitted phase spectra during the experiment are shown in (b). The phase shift is determined by the mass loading of the BSA on the sensor surface. (c) Black, red and blue dots represent resonance frequency phase shifts upon the adsorption of 0.1 mg/ml, 1 mg/ml and 10 mg/ml BSA solutions, respectively. Black, red and blue lines are exponential fit of the phase shift of the transmitted power at f_0 during the BSA adsorption. The inset shows the characteristic adsorption times (τ) of the three kinetics vs. the initial concentration of BSA in the solution. Red line represents the expected trend of these data.